

A seedling root dip in 0.02% isofenphos followed by phorate G broadcast at 1 kg ai/ha or implanted 0.75 kg ai/ha as mudballs at 25 DT performed equally well. A foliar spray of quinalphos at 0.5 kg ai/ha 15, 30, and 45 DT was significantly inferior to the other treatments, but control was superior to that in the unprotected Jaya crop.

To keep GM incidence below the economic injury level on susceptible varieties, it is necessary to combine a seedling root dip with a granular insecticide applied 25 DT. Additional insecticide applications were not economical. Resistant Shakti yielded >4 t/ha with no plant protection.

An economic evaluation of GM control methods showed that on Jaya all controls produced more profit than no treatment (Table 2). Including phorate G in the control schedule gave > \$300 profit/ha compared to \$86 with quinalphos alone. The benefit-cost ratio indicated that seedling root dip followed by broadcast phorate G at 25 DT gave maximum profit. The second best treatment was phorate applications at 25 and 45 DT. Phorate G implanted in mudballs at 25 DT following seedling root dip was effective and economical, but is a cumbersome process and may be less acceptable to farmers.

Maximum protection cost more than \$100/ha, which was high for a farmer of marginal land. Seedling root dip followed by phorate G at 25 DT gave the maximum benefit-cost ratio of 8.78:1 and cost only \$39/ha.

Table 1. Integrated GM control on Jaya, Bhubaneswar, India.

Insecticide treatment	Silvershoot (%) ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1979	1980	1979	1980
Maximum protection ^b	4.7	5.4	4.9	4.5
Seedling root dip + phorate G broadcast at 25 DT	6.9	8.0	3.9	3.9
Seedling root dip + phorate G mudball at 25 DT	8.5	11.5	4.4	4.2
Seedling root dip + phorate G broadcast at 20 and 45 DT	11.4	7.6	4.1	4.2
Foliar spray of quinalphos at 15, 30, and 45 DT	32.8	45.9	2.9	2.0
Untreated check	42.0	63.2	1.7	0.8
Untreated check (Shakti)	2.3	4.3	4.4	4.1
SE (m) ±	1.4	1.8	0.2	0.2
CD (0.05)	4.2	5.5	0.5	0.5

^a Mean of 3 replications at 50 DT. ^b Seedling root dip in 0.02% isofenphos for 3 h with 1% urea + phorate G 1 kg ai/ha at 20, 40, 60 DT + quinalphos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha at 85 DT. Phorate G was applied at 1.0 kg ai/ha per application and mudballs at 0.75 kg ai/ha.

Table 2. Economics of rice GM control on Jaya, Bhubaneswar, India.

Insecticide treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Gross profit ^b (US\$/ha)	Cost of insecticide application ^c (US\$/ha)	Net gain ^d (US\$/ha)	Gain from insecticide ^e (US\$/ha)	Benefit cost ^f
Maximum protection ^g	4.71 a	612	115	497	333	3.89
Seedling root dip + phorate G broadcast	3.90 b	504	39	466	302	8.78
Seedling root dip + phorate mud ball at 25 DT	4.3 ab	562	61	501	337	6.51
Phorate G broadcast at 20 and 45 DT	4.1 b	536	54	481	318	6.87
Foliar spray of quinalphos at 15, 30, and 45 DT	2.4 c	317	67	250	86	2.24
Untreated check	1.3 d	164	0	164	—	—
Untreated check (Shakti)	4.2 ab	547	0	547	—	—

^a Av yield in 1979 and 1980 wet seasons at 13% moisture. Separation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^b Cost of yield calculated at \$0.13/kg paddy. ^c Cost of insecticide + labor calculated at rates prevailing at the time of the experiment. ^d Gross profit of treatment minus gross profit of control + cost of insecticide application. ^e Net gain of treatment minus net gain of control. ^f Gain from insecticide + cost of insecticide application. ^g Details of maximum protection in Table 1.

GM-resistant Shakti, with no insecticide treatment, gave a \$547 profit/ha. □

Influence of planting date on rice whorl maggot (RWM) infestation

D. Sundararaju, Indian Council of Agricultural Research Complex, Ela, Old Goa 403402, India

To study the effect of planting time on RWM *Hydrellia* spp incidence in kharif, Jaya was planted every 2 wk in 40-m² plots with 5 replications beginning Jun and ending in Jul for 3 seasons – 1979-81. No insecticide was applied.

Total leaves and RWM-damaged leaves on 10 randomly selected hills from each plot were counted 15 and 30 d

Influence of planting date on RWM incidence at Goa, India. ^a

Planting date	Mean leaf damage (%)					Grain yield (t/ha)		
	15 DT		30 DT					
	1980	1981	1979	1980	1981	1979	1980	1981
7 Jun	6.1 b	0.8 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.7 a	4.2 a	6.9 a	5.1 a
22 Jun	8.2 b	5.4 ab	5.5 b	4.2 b	2.3 b	3.6 b	6.2 a	4.7 b
7 Jul	3.7 a	8.0 b	25.8 c	9.0 c	2.3 b	2.8 c	4.7 b	3.2 c
22 Jul	17.2 c	12.5 b	30.1 c	18.5 d	3.8 b	2.6 c	4.2 b	1.6 d

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. DT = days after transplanting.

after transplanting and percent damage was calculated (see table). The early

planted crop had significantly less damage than the late planted crop. □